

titanium, vanadium and cerium by hydrogen peroxide. Molybdenum, tungsten, niobium and tantalum were removed by keeping the acid concentration high and by hot filtration when zirconium alone remained in solution. After filtration, zirconium was precipitated in the usual way at the required pH. The interference of hafnium could not however be removed.

Standard Deviation :

The standard deviation for sixteen determinations of zirconium (containing 8.8 mg of the metal oxide) with N-phenyl-o-tolyl hydroxylamine was ± 0.012 .

Metal ion Added	ZrO ₂ Taken (mg)	ZrO ₂ Found (mg)	Relative mean error (%)	Metal ion Added	ZrO ₂ Taken (mg)	ZrO ₂ Found (mg)	Relative mean error (%)
Fe(II)				WO ₅ ⁺			
80 mg	8.80	8.80	+0.057	60 mg	8.80	8.80	± 0
80 mg	8.80	8.81		60 mg	8.80	8.80	
Ti(IV)				Nb ⁺			
100 mg	8.80	8.79	-0.171	50 mg	8.80	8.81	+0.171
100 mg	8.80	8.78		50 mg	8.80	8.82	
Ce(IV)				Ta ⁺			
50 mg	8.80	8.80	+0.057	10 mg	8.80	8.78	-0.057
50 mg	8.80	8.81		10 mg	8.80	8.81	
MoO ₄ ²⁻				VO ₅ ⁻			
100 mg	8.80	8.78	-0.171	60 mg	8.80	8.81	+0.057
100 mg	8.80	8.79		60 mg	8.80	8.80	

References

1. A. K. MAJUMDAR and B. K. PAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 43.
2. A. K. MAJUMDAR and G. DAS, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1964, **31**, 147.
3. A. K. MAJUMDAR and M. K. DAS, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1970, **50**, 243.
4. B. K. PAL, Ph.D. Thesis, Jadavpur University, 1964.
5. J. WELCHER FRANK, *Organic Analytical Reagents*, Vol. III, 1st published 1947, p. 379.
6. D. E. RYAN, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1960, **38**, 2488.
7. I. P. ALIMARIN and S. TUNG, Chiaing Tse, *Talanta*, 1962, **9**, 9.

Studies on EGTA Complexes of VO₂⁺ by Spectrophotometry

ARABINDA K. DAS* and AMIYA KUMAR CHAKRABURTTY

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University,
Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 13 February 1979, revised 17 March
1980, accepted 19 May 1980

EDTA (H₄Y) forms a complex compound VO₂Y⁻³ with pentavalent vanadium with stability constant, log K=18.05 in 0.1M NaClO₄ medium. At pH values below about 3.5 the species VO₂HY⁻² is

formed and the acidic dissociation constant of this compound is $pK_a = 3.60^1$. The equilibrium constant for the reaction $VO_2^+ + Y^{4-} = VO_2Y^{-3}$ in 0.1M KCl medium was also determined by other authors² to be log K=15.55. Nothing is known about the complex formed by pentavalent vanadium with ethylene glycol bis(aminoethyl ether)-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid (EGTA or H₄L), a complexing agent analogous to EDTA.

Experimental

EGTA was obtained from Pfaltz and Bauer, Inc. and it was purified by crystallisation from hot water. Ammonium vanadate was E. Merck AG grade. All spectrophotometric studies were made by using an EC spectrophotometer model GS 865A and all pH measurements were made by using an EC expanded scale pH meter model pH 821A.

To a known volume of an ammonium vanadate solution was added a known solution of disodium salt of EGTA. The pH of this mixture was adjusted with dilute HClO₄ or NaOH solution. The whole mixture was then brought to a known volume in a measuring flask while the ionic strength was kept at approximately 0.1M by addition of NaClO₄ solution. The temperature was Ca. 22°. The pH of each of these solutions was measured in the pH meter with an agaragar-KCl salt bridge. Next, the absorbance of the same solution was measured in the spectrophotometer. All the measurements were carried out at 22°.

After a study was made with pH versus molar absorbance of the solution at 340 nm in the whole pH range (2 to 13), the data was plotted in Fig. 1. Next, in the pH range where the formation of the

Fig. 1. Molar absorbance of vanadium at 340 nm in an excess of EGTA as a function of pH + C_V = 2 × 10⁻³ M, C_{EGTA} = 1 × 10⁻² M.

* Present address : Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104.

concerned species occur the absorbances at different pH's were measured at different wavelengths. The experimental data are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF THE ACIDIC DISSOCIATION CONSTANT

C_V (M)	C_{EGTA} (M)	pH	$A_b^{2.0}$	$A_a^{2.0}$	$A_m^{2.0}$	pK _a
2×10^{-3}	1×10^{-3}	5.4	0.61	0.31	0.33	5.546
2×10^{-3}	1×10^{-3}	6.1	0.61	0.31	0.39	5.539
2×10^{-3}	1×10^{-3}	6.6	0.61	0.31	0.49	5.424
2×10^{-3}	1×10^{-3}	6.9	0.61	0.31	0.56	5.201
1×10^{-3}	1×10^{-3}	5.6	0.42	0.23	0.34	5.462
1×10^{-3}	1×10^{-3}	6.0	0.42	0.23	0.38	5.426
1×10^{-3}	1×10^{-3}	6.4	0.42	0.23	0.40	5.471
1×10^{-3}	1×10^{-3}	6.8	0.42	0.23	0.41	5.545
1×10^{-4}	1×10^{-3}	5.5	0.19	0.09	0.14	5.500
1×10^{-4}	1×10^{-3}	5.9	0.19	0.09	0.16	5.532
1×10^{-4}	1×10^{-3}	6.3	0.19	0.09	0.17	5.698
1×10^{-4}	1×10^{-3}	6.5	0.19	0.09	0.18	5.546

known equation :

$$\frac{C_b}{C_a} = \frac{A_m - A_a}{A_b - A_m} \quad (3)$$

where $C_a = [VO_2HL^{-2}]$, $C_b = [VO_2L^{-3}]$

A_b = measured absorbance in the pH range 7.0-8.2,

A_a = measured absorbance in the pH range 2.7-4.5, and

A_m = measured absorbance at the intermediate pH between 4.5 to 7.0.

The expression for the dissociation constant of the species VO_2HL^{-2} is given by

$$k_a = \frac{[H^+].C_b}{C_a} \quad \dots (4)$$

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF THE FORMATION CONSTANT

$C_V = C_{EGTA}$ (M)	pH	$\log \beta_{HL}$	$A_{VO_2HL}^{2.0}$	$A_{VO_2}^{2.0}$	$A^{2.0}$	α	$\log K_{VO_2HL}$
1×10^{-3}	3.5	-4.93	0.54	0.23	0.35	0.613	7.946
1×10^{-3}	4.0	-4.41	0.54	0.23	0.39	0.484	7.754
1×10^{-3}	4.5	-3.90	0.54	0.23	0.45	0.290	7.830
1×10^{-3}	5.0	-3.40	0.54	0.23	0.49	0.193	7.737
5×10^{-3}	3.8	-4.57	0.33	0.15	0.23	0.555	7.730
5×10^{-3}	4.3	-4.11	0.33	0.15	0.27	0.333	7.186
5×10^{-3}	4.8	-3.60	0.33	0.15	0.29	0.111	7.761
5×10^{-3}	5.3	-3.10	0.33	0.15	0.32	0.055	7.896

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 shows that ammonium vanadate solution when titrated with disodium salt of EGTA, the acidity constant remains the same in the pH range 7.0-8.2 until the equivalent point :

In solutions at pH values below 7.0, another complex is formed,

The analogous EDTA complexes, e.g., VO_2Y^{-3} and VO_2HY^{-2} have been established earlier^{1,3}. For strongly acidic solutions (e.g., at pH below 9.3), the acid ligand EGTA starts separating out. In the most basic solutions (e.g., at pH values higher than 8.2) vanadates are formed⁴.

At a particular wavelength, it is possible to calculate the concentrations of different species by well

Combining equations (3) and (4)

$$k_a = \frac{[H^+].(A_m - A_a)}{(A_b - A_m)} \quad \dots (5)$$

The expression for the formation constant of the species VO_2HL^{-2} is given by a similar equation described previously¹.

$$K_{VO_2HL} = \frac{(1 - \alpha)}{2\beta_{HL}C} \quad \dots (6)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{A_{VO_2HL} - A}{A_{VO_2HL} - A_{VO_2}} \quad \dots (7)$$

β_{HL} = fraction of EGTA not bound to VO_2^+ appears as HL^{-3} and

$$\beta_{HL} = \frac{[H^+].\beta_L}{k_4} \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\text{with } \beta_L = \left[\frac{[\text{H}^+]^4}{k_1 k_2 k_3 k_4} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^3}{k_2 k_3 k_4} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_3 k_4} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_4} + 1 \right]^{-1} \quad \dots (9)$$

The values of acid dissociation constants k_1 , k_2 , etc., were obtained from a handbook⁴.

However, the expression for the formation constant will be

$$K_{\text{VO}_2\text{L}} = \frac{K_{\text{VO}_2\text{HL}} \cdot K_{\text{VO}_2\text{HL}}}{k_4} \quad \dots (10)$$

The obtained values are compared with corresponding values of EDTA complexes^{1,2}. It transpires that the species $\text{VO}_2\text{H}(\text{EDTA})^{-2}$ ($pK_a = 3.60$) is more acidic than $\text{VO}_2\text{H}(\text{EGTA})^{-2}$ ($pK_a = 5.49$) whereas the stability values of the species $\text{VO}_2\text{H}(\text{EDTA})^{-2}$ (11.39) and $\text{VO}_2(\text{EDTA})^{-3}$ (18.05) are more than the corresponding $\text{VO}_2\text{H}(\text{EGTA})^{-2}$ (7.73) and $\text{VO}_2(\text{EGTA})^{-3}$ (11.18). This may be attributed to the steric effect due to longer linking chain between the two nitrogen atoms separating the carboxylic acid groups apart in the EGTA molecule as compared to the shorter separation in EDTA. The plateau region of the $\text{VO}_2^+-\text{EGTA}$ system (Fig. 1) is shorter than that of $\text{VO}_2^+-\text{EDTA}$ system¹ which may be due to the same reason.

References

1. A. RINGBOM, S. SIITONEN and B. SKRIFVAR, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1957, **11**, 551.
2. L. PRZYBOROWSKI, G. SCHWARZENBACH and TH. ZIMMERMAN, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1965, **48**, 1556.
3. F. J. C. ROSSOTTI and H. ROSSOTTI, *Acta Chem. Scand.* 1956, **10**, 957.
4. Stability Constants, (Supplement No. 1), Special Publication 25, Chemical Society, London, 1971.

Estimation of Thiourea, Allyl Thiourea and Toly Thiourea by Sodium N-Chloro-*p*-Toluene Sulphonamide†

K. V. UMA and S. M. MAYANNA*

Department of Chemistry, Central College, Bangalore-1

Manuscript received 7 February 1979, revised 29 May 1979, accepted 19 May 1980

THE mechanism of oxidation of thioureas has been the subject of many investigations¹. Thiourea and its derivatives are generally oxidised to the corresponding disulphide², although instances of oxidation beyond the disulphide stage are also known³. Several oxidising agents have been used for assaying these compounds⁴⁻⁹ and an excellent

review of the subject by Balwanth Singh *et al*¹⁰ is noteworthy. Thioureas find a number of industrial applications in rubber vulcanization, electrodeposition of metals, corrosion inhibition, photography and in polymer, textile and agricultural industries. Sodium N-chloro-*p*-toluene sulphonamide (Chloramine-T), has been used in estimations of thiourea and its derivatives in slightly concentrated sulphuric acid and at high temperatures¹¹. However, this method is less accurate because of the decomposition of chloramine-T at high temperatures¹². The present communication deals with the estimation of thiourea (TU), allyl thiourea (ATU) and toly thiourea (TTU) by chloramine-T under mild experimental conditions.

Chloramine-T (E. Merck) was purified¹³ and used. All other reagents were of analytical grade. Solutions were prepared using triple distilled water. Chloramine-T (CAT) solution was standardised by iodometric method.

Since the oxidation reactions are not instantaneous under the given experimental conditions and the optimum medium contains sufficient amount of HCl, direct visual titration and potentiometric titration were not carried out. Hence, back titration procedure was adopted for the estimations of these compounds.

In preliminary experiments with CAT, known amounts of TU, ATU and TTU prepared in the appropriate buffer¹⁴ or solvent were added to a known and excessive volume (10-20%) of CAT solution in iodine flasks at 30°. The reaction mixtures were set aside for various intervals of time, with occasional shaking. Then the excess of CAT was determined by back titration. A typical set of results for the extent of oxidation of TU, ATU and TTU in different media are given in Table 1. Oxidations of TU and ATU are not reproducible and

TABLE 1—EXTENT OF OXIDATION OF THIOUREA, ALLYL THIOUREA AND TOLYL THIOUREA IN DIFFERENT MEDIA WITH EXCESS OF CHLORAMINE-T AT 30°C

Medium	%Oxidation			Medium	%Oxidation		
	TU	ATU	TTU		TU	ATU	TTU
0.6M HCl	100.1	100.2	48.0	pH*2	77.4	91.1	94.4
0.5M HCl	99.2	100.1	49.6	pH†3	80.3	93.0	85.8
0.4M HCl	97.7	100.0	49.6	pH**4	84.5	93.6	70.5
0.3M HCl	96.5	97.0	50.4	pH**5	92.1	94.0	68.7
0.2M HCl	93.6	92.1	51.1	pH**6	95.0	96.0	65.6
pH*1	92.9	89.5	70.4	pH††7	96.5	98.0	63.0

[CAT] taken $5 \times 10^{-3}M$, [TU], [ATU] and [TTU] taken $7 \times 10^{-4}M$
 *HCl-KCl buffer, **Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer,
 †Potassiumbipthalate-HCl buffer. ††Borax-boric acid buffer.
 Time : 30 minutes for ATU and TTU, 45 minutes for TU.

non-stoichiometric in various media other than HCl solutions. The % oxidation increases gradually as the concentration of HCl increases, but the increase becomes rapid at or above 0.5N HCl. However,

† Presented in the Annual Convention of Chemists, 1978.